

REDEMOS

RECONFIGURING EU DEMOCRACY
SUPPORT. TOWARDS A SUSTAINED
DEMOS IN THE EU'S EASTERN
NEIGHBOURHOOD

Travel handbook

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1. Introduction

The safety and security of everybody involved in the implementation of REDEMOS – particularly its researchers and research participants – is a top-level priority, and the project places utmost emphasis on the do-no-significant-harm principle. REDEMOS involves human participants conducting field research in non-EU countries such as Moldova, Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan and Ukraine, i.e. in countries that – to varying degrees – are exposed to different forms of political rule, ranging from hybrid democratic systems to full-blown authoritarian governance, and that are suffering from secessionism, territorial occupation and even territorial conflict and full-blown war. Obviously, as the tragic case of the late Italian Phd student Giulio Regeni, who was tortured to death by Egyptian security forces while conducting field research on trade unions in Egypt in 2016 demonstrates, field research can be risky and dangerous. REDEMOS rejects the notion that there is anything particularly “honorable” in conducting field research in fragile/unsafe spaces, that such conduct is a particular sign of researchers’ resilience, and/or that risk and danger are supposed to be embraced. Thus, this handbook is first and foremost supposed to contribute to the reduction of risk and promote safer field research and, at the same time, underscore REDEMOS’ duty of care. It is destined to offer REDEMOS researchers engaging in field research some key pointers and guidance on how to cope with the multiple challenges and risks that field work in fragile and sometimes even potentially hostile and dangerous environments entails. Whilst it is supposed to improve REDEMOS researchers’ awareness and preparations for, as well as practice of, field work in challenging settings, the travel handbook does not aim at comprehensiveness. This is due to the fact that (a) it is a “living document” that will continue to be updated throughout the project’s lifetime, adjusting it also to supposedly changing circumstances, and that (b) very relevant volumes, addressing the issue of risk and safety in field research in the social sciences, have been published recently, offering already highly informative and detailed overviews of aspects and factors that need to be considered before heading into the field. Two extremely useful volumes in this regard are:

- Grimm, J.J., Koehler, K., Lust, E.M., Saliba, I. and I. Schierenbeck (2020). *Safer Field Research in the Social Sciences*, London: SAGE.
- Glasius, M., de Lange, M., Bartman, J., Dalmaso, E., Lv, A., Del Sordi, A., Michaelsen, M., and K. Ruijgrok (2018). *Research, Ethics and Risk in the Authoritarian Field*, Cham: Springer.

In addition, several international organizations have published guides that contain valuable information which can also be utilised by REDEMOS researchers. Among these are:

- Council of the European Union (2008). *Field Security Handbook*, Brussels: Council of the European Union.
- Smyth, F. (2012). *CPJ Journalist Security Guide*. New York: Committee to Protect Journalists.

- UNESCO and Reporters without Borders (2016). *Safety Guide for Journalists: A Handbook for Reporters in High-Risk Environments*, CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform.
- United Nations (2006). *United Nations Field Security Handbook*. New York: United Nations.

REDEMOS draws on the definition provided for by Grimm et. al. (2020) and distinguishes between three different types of threat/risk:

1. “Physical threats, or threats to individuals’ bodies range from acute threats such as kidnappings and murders, to denied entry, detainment and deportation, or physical illness and accidents – often the most common physical threats in research processes. In addition, REDEMOS adds to this enumeration threats to individuals’ lives as a result of exposure to ongoing violent conflict.
2. Psychological threats are the mental stress that often comes from research in dangerous environments or when studying sensitive issues, whether from the stress of hearing accounts of violent incidents or social ostracization from those who oppose your research. The psychological pressure and stress you might experience in the field can affect your ability to assess potential changes in the risk environment.
3. Threats to data security are related to the information you produce and collect through your research or the communication with interlocutors. Threats to data security can have physical and psychological consequences. Individuals risk being harassed, arrested, or even killed if data is compromised; they can suffer identity theft or have bank accounts drained; or suffer and protected finds defamation and psychological stress when information that is intended to be confidential and protected finds its way into the wrong hands.”

As is pointed out by Grimm et. al. (2020), these threats/risks are not necessarily limited to the time spent in the field. For example, some researchers may want to return to the field at a later stage and, therefore, need to adjust their actions and behaviour with the “next time” in mind whilst other researchers or research participants – local consortium partners, assistants, interpreters, respondents, etc. – will even remain on the ground once field research has ended. Yet other researchers may even be exposed to threats/risks once they have returned from their field research and concluded their data collection. Put differently: multiple reasons can be identified why it is important to be aware of and ideally map field research-related threats/risks and develop threats/risks mitigation strategies prior to embarking on a field trip. In broad terms, three different phases can be identified in this context, notably:

- (a) Threats/risks assessment prior to field research (the “before”);
- (b) Handling of threats/risks while conducting field research (the “during”);
- (c) Dealing with threats/risks upon completion of field research (the “after”).

2. Threats/risks assessment prior to field research

Before going into the field and conducting field research it is imperative that REDEMOS researchers engage in a comprehensive threats/risks assessment in order to be fully aware of the three threat/risk categories, as outlined above, i.e. physical threats/risks, psychological threats/risks, and digital threats/risks. Such an assessment is crucial with respect to taking seriously the do-no-significant-harm principle and it requires awareness of the distinction between “threat” and “risk”. As far as the former is concerned, REDEMOS subscribes to the notion that “threat” describes a phenomenon that can inflict damage, pain, injury and even death on someone and/or something (i.e. electronic equipment) in response to a certain action or inaction. By the same token, REDEMOS defines “risk” as the probability of the occurrence of a certain incident that generates undesired and/or negative consequences. Risk is inevitably marked by uncertainty and two distinct opposites, notably, on one hand, ontological risk and, on the other, epistemic risk. The former implies that incidents and consequences exist independently of a risk analysis whilst the latter does not exist in its own right but rather is the individual assessment of a given situation by the researcher.

In any case, REDEMOS researchers are strongly encouraged to thoroughly think about the risks and threats they may be faced with during and after they embark on field research, and one way of pursuing this is offered by Grimm et. al. (2020) who offer a risk matrix that links the probability of the occurrence of a certain threat with the impact it will generate vis-à-vis research participants.

Table 1: Risk matrix

		Impact				
		Negligible	Minor	Moderate	Severe	Critical
Likelihood	Very high	Low	Medium	High	Very high	Unacceptable
	High	Low	Medium	High	High	Very high
	Moderate	Low	Low	Medium	High	High
	Low	Low	Low	Low	Medium	Medium
	Very Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low

Source: Grimm et al (2020), p. 18.

REDEMOS subscribes to the utility of such a matrix – or rather matrixes if more than one risk is being identified – as it helps to systematise and thus visualise risk in relation to impact/consequence. The individual cells can be used to list every single threat that has been identified in the risk assessment and relate it to the vulnerabilities and capacities of the research participants. In that sense, this matrix underlines the need for REDEMOS researchers to draft a risk assessment plan that allows them to put in place preventive and/or protective

measures which help to reduce the likelihood or the potential impact of an identified threat. By the same token, and useful as such a matrix is, two caveats are in order. First, the “low-unacceptable continuum” is – *strictu sensu* – a subjective determination and ideally, with a view to avoid bias and miscalculation, should be generated not just by one researcher but by the entire research team contributing to a work package. Secondly, such a matrix cannot be static but rather needs to be updated and adjusted in line with developments in the field. In other words, such a risk matrix transcends the first and the second, and potentially even the third phase.

Also, it goes without saying that such a matrix is part and parcel of a much broader assessment that inevitably requires engaging with three broad questions. These are:

- A. What threat/risk factors *external* to REDEMOS researchers exist in the national/local/regional setting in which field research is supposed to take place?
- B. What threat/risk factors *directly linked* to REDEMOS researchers exist that may increase their vulnerability and capacity to conduct field research in the selected national/local/regional setting?
- C. Are the potentially identifiable threats of a direct or indirect nature?

As regards the first question, it is obvious that such factors are directly related to geographical, political, economic, social and ideology-related characteristics and in particular to the security situation in the field. The second question, however, revolves directly around features specific to the researchers themselves, such as, for example, their identity, gender, ethnic/national background, language skills, sexual orientation, religious belonging, whether the researcher travels alone or in a larger group, the type of methods and methodologies used, etc. In contrast, the third question cuts across the first two. Whilst direct threats are always both intentional and directed at the researcher(s) conducting field research, indirect threats are also intentional but do not necessarily target the researcher(s) in the field. Instead, these are particularly about (tangible or intangible) red lines that are not supposed to be crossed.

In addition to the above, REDEMOS researchers should follow four key steps as far as threat/risk assessment is concerned before they go into the field:

1. REDEMOS researchers are strongly encouraged to check the websites of their respective Ministries of Foreign Affairs and consult the latest travel advice relating to the country/region in question and, ideally, juxtapose it with the travel advice of other reliable government sources.
2. REDEMOS researchers are strongly encouraged to utilise the Early Warning Mechanism (as described in D10.4, operational as of 1 May 2023 and run by the Project Management Team (PMT)) and check if it lists any warnings. The EWM is an instrument that revolves around informed warning and functions as a rapid response mechanism: all REDEMOS partners in the EU’s eastern neighbourhood closely monitor local and regional developments and alert the PMT without any delay in the event a

situation occurs that may affect the safety and security of REDEMOS researchers and research participants. This is being done either through a dedicated Teams channel (“Early Warning Mechanism EWM”) or a particular phone number (+47.462.858.21) that allows partners to alert the PMT at any point in time. In a second step, the latter will then within two working days engage – also by involving as many consortium partners as possible – in obtaining as comprehensive an overview as is possible of the development in question and subsequently issue an information/warning alert to affected partners. Such alerts will contain brief summaries and assessments of the incident as well as clear-cut recommendations. In the event of developments that are of a nature that might seriously jeopardise the implementation of partners’ field research, the PMT and the respective work package leader(s) will deliberate and jointly assess the matter and subsequently reach a decision.

3. In addition to utilizing the EWM, REDEMOS researchers are strongly encouraged to consult with their local consortium partners in the country in which field research is planned to take place and seek their advice and guidance. Moreover, REDEMOS researchers are invited to also consult with the PMT which stands ready to provide informed advice.
4. REDEMOS researchers are strongly encouraged to draft contingency plans, ideally enabling them to respond to as many previously identified threats/risks as quickly and smoothly as possible. Basic elements of such contingency plans are, for example:
 - A. Ensure that all identity and travel documents are in order
 - Validity;
 - Visa;
 - Passports do not feature supposedly “compromising” stamps;
 - B. Refresh and complete potentially relevant trainings (on resilience, mental health, occupational health, etc.)
 - C. Predefine measures regarding the handling of potential within-research team problems
 - D. Predefine who to contact in the event of an emergency and be in possession of the contact details of all relevant contacts
 - Embassy;
 - Work package leader;
 - PMT;
 - Local partner, etc.
 - E. Obtain knowledge of existing formal (legal frameworks) and informal rules (social norms, red lines, taboos, etc.) in the field site
 - F. Familiarise yourself with potential diseases in or close to the field site
 - G. Conclude travel insurance and health insurance
 - The PMT abstains from making any concrete recommendations, though there are many well-known international insurance providers such as, for example, Global Rescue, IMG, Allianz, Cigna, that provide suitable and reliable services.

- H. Be familiar with the procedures of purchasing a local SIM card
- I. Alter or even suspend social media presence for the duration of fieldwork
- J. Create an offloading structure for moving digital data safely out of the field
- K. Reflect on – as much as this is possible *ex-ante* – the visibility of your methods/methodology and how it may impact your safety and security while in the field
- L. Draft an exit strategy allowing for an early departure from the field site
 - Clarify *a priori* how to enter and leave the field site
 - Clarify *a priori* how best to leave your rented accommodation in the event of an emergency situation
 - Clarify *a priori* how reliable and affordable local transportation is
 - Clarify *a priori* how safe the local road system is
 - Clarify *a priori* where the closest airport/border crossing is in relation to your envisaged field location

3. Handling of threats/risks while conducting field research

Upon arrival at the field research site, REDEMOS researchers are strongly encouraged to familiarise themselves immediately with the key infrastructure or what the relevant literature calls “research ecology”. In other words, it is important to generate awareness of (a) strategically relevant places which are particularly exposed (police stations, squares where protests usually take place, government buildings, etc.), and (b) of key routes to sites relevant in the context of the field research. This implies familiarizing oneself with, for example, relevant bus stops, the location of taxi stands, the way to one’s embassy or the airport, etc.

It is recommended while being in the field to continuously update oneself with respect to local, national and regional developments so as to stay abreast of potentially rapidly changing circumstances. In this sense, regularly utilizing both local *and* relevant international (social) media is highly important, and there are many reliable – both national and international – sources REDEMOS researchers may want to resort to. Whilst for national information sources in the EU’s Eastern neighbourhood countries, REDEMOS researchers are strongly encouraged to consult with local consortium partners and other field researchers, they are advised to regularly check news sources such as, for example, [Radio Free Europe/Radio Liberty](#), , [OC-Media](#), [New Eastern Europe](#), [Caucasus Analytical Digest](#), [Balkan Insight](#), regularly updated [analysis, commentaries and reports](#) by the Warsaw-based Centre for Eastern Studies, and the International Crisis Group’s [CrisisWatch](#). In addition, the United States Overseas Security Advisory Council offers both so-called [country security reports](#) and [daily travel advisories and alerts](#) from US embassies all over the world.

REDEMOS researchers are strongly encouraged to pursue strategies related to their used methods that minimise their exposure and visibility. Obviously, the extent to which this is possible is largely determined by the methods chosen as, for example, qualitative interviews can be pursued in countless places with low exposure and thus visibility whilst, for example, ethnographic methods may inevitably entail a certain degree of exposure and visibility. By the same token, it is of utmost importance that, for example, researchers are fully aware of the nature of research questions they may ask, the connotations these may entail, who these questions are being addressed to and how these research participants may perceive them. In other words, whilst avoiding deceiving research participants, situations (particularly in autocratic settings) may arise during which the researcher(s) may need to adjust their research questions and even methods to the setting and potentially unfolding dynamics.

In particular when conducting field research in non-democratic settings in the EU's eastern neighbourhood, there is a risk that REDEMOS researchers might be exposed to scrutiny and checks by national security services. In this context, there is a risk that laptops and mobile phones may be searched or – in the worst case – confiscated. Against the backdrop of this possibility, REDEMOS researchers are encouraged to store their data and other sensitive information on a safe digital cloud and clear the browsing history on a daily basis.

Should the need arise for REDEMOS researchers while being in the field to engage local fixers, interpreters, drivers, and other persons relevant to the implementation of the field research, it is of major importance that these individuals can be trusted. Thus, it is recommended to involve local consortium partners and other trustworthy contacts and seek their advice with a view to identify reliable local support staff. Obviously, once these have been recruited, clear-cut agreements, stipulating duties, responsibilities and remuneration, should be concluded. Also, it is not just a matter of courtesy to treat local support staff kindly and with respect, but it is also a “safety issue” of sorts as a relationship based on trust, respect and acknowledgment or lack thereof may either enhance or reduce researchers’ (sense of) safety and security in the field site.

While being in the field, REDEMOS researchers have a responsibility to ensure – as much as this is possible – the safety of their research participants and local support staff. Obviously, this entails that they are being fully informed of their rights and that their identities will be handled in line with existing GDPR regulations. Also, it entails that data is being collected and stored in a way that guarantees the safety and integrity of both the researcher(s) and the research participants (for more details on this, see the REDEMOS Data Management Plan). Moreover, it entails that research participants – particularly in autocratic and repressive settings – cannot be requested to engage in interaction in places where they feel/are unsafe or can even be under surveillance. In other words, it is of utmost importance to carefully choose the interview space and consider research participants’ ability and/or willingness to travel to and from that chosen location.

REDEMOS researchers are strongly encouraged, while being in the field, to not fall into the trap of complacency towards existing threats and risks. In particular in field sites that are

particularly volatile and during longer field research trips, REDEMOS researchers are recommended to regularly “take a step back” and spend time on reflecting on their situation rather than conducting field research without a break. Reassess risks and threats regularly! Such time-outs can be complemented by keeping a digital field research diary. Such a diary would serve as a notebook in which the researcher(s) would write down not just research-related information but in particular field research-related challenges as well as observations made with respect to potential and/or existing threats. If such a diary was used, it is important to keep it digitally safe, for example on a cloud, so it cannot be accessed by others.

Closely related to the previous point is the fact that REDEMOS researchers are strongly encouraged to look after themselves and maintain their health throughout the entire field research. This also entails ensuring that they have – in those cases where this applies – a sufficient stock of medication and ideally are familiar with local healthcare providers and what to do in case of a medical emergency.

REDEMOS researchers are strongly encouraged while being in the field to communicate on a regular basis with their team leader/work package leader and ideally the local consortium partner. The frequency of this regular communication and providing updates on both the implementation of the field research and researchers’ safety obviously depends on the setting in which field research takes place and can vary from case to case and thus the initial and evolving threat/risk assessment. By the same token, it is important that the communication takes place via a pre-agreed medium (phone, skype, whatsapp, telegram, signal, etc.) and that the contents of the messages are of a nature that – in a worst-case scenario – allow the recipient of the communication to understand any potential irregularity.

In the event that REDEMOS team members, whilst conducting fieldwork in parts of the EU’s eastern neighbourhood, will be affected by unforeseen developments that have the potential to impact their security and safety, the PMT will immediately establish contact and urge them to consult both with their respective work package leaders and seek travel advice from their respective foreign ministries. At the same time, the PMT will closely consult with STEERG members and the project officer at the European Commission in charge of the REDEMOS project with a view to reach a swift decision regarding any potential action to be taken.

4. Dealing with threats/risks upon completion of field research

Though it is quite common among researchers who conduct field research to mainly focus on *a priori* threat/risk assessment and how to handle threats and risks while being in the field, it is important to raise awareness for the fact that researchers and research participants in particular may still be exposed to threats and risks even after the actual field research has ended.

For example, in EU eastern neighbourhood countries such as Belarus and Azerbaijan where researchers working on democracy-related aspects are considered by the local regimes as threats to the national security, there is a high risk that research partners might face ill-treatment after they have participated in the research. This can range, for example, from being exposed to surveillance and systematic reputational damage, to more extreme forms such as interrogation, arrest and even torture. In other words, REDEMOS researchers do have a responsibility vis-à-vis their research participants (and by extension their families) also once field research has ended and, therefore, are strongly advised to have a plan in place that offers guidance as to how to ensure research participants' safety and security in a post-field research scenario. This entails – as will be discussed in more detail in the Data Management Plan – anonymization of research participants' identities, and sometimes even field sites and organizations visited, though the risk remains that research subjects can indeed be identified.

By the same token, REDEMOS researchers need to be aware that they themselves upon return from the field might be exposed to unwanted contact with the intelligence services of their home country, potentially being interested in the findings of the field research and wanting to learn about individual research participants and their views. Thus, REDEMOS researchers are strongly advised to prepare for such a possibility so as to be informed about their rights as well existing legal frameworks and, for example, existing legislation related to national security or counterterrorism.

Lastly, whilst for many researchers going into the field has become a routine practice which, once field research has ended, serves the exclusive purpose of transforming raw data into publishable scholarly work, REDEMOS researchers are encouraged to go beyond the rather narrow nexus of data generation and data interpretation and engage in sharing field work experiences with other academics and in particular early career researchers who have not yet gathered much field research experience themselves. Such activities, which can be organised at faculty level and/or national and international conferences, provide REDEMOS researchers with an opportunity to engage in a more systematic ex-post reflection of the many dimensions of the field research and, at the same time, act as transmitters of knowledge and highly valuable coping strategies.

5. Further readings

Ansorg, N. (2019). *Conducting Fieldwork in Security-Sensitive Environments*, London: SAGE.

Davies, J. and D. Spencer (2010). *Emotions in the Field: The Psychology and Anthropology of Fieldwork Experience*. Palo Alto, CA: Stanford University Press.

Durán-Martínez, A. (2014). *Building an Effective Research Safety Protocol and Emergency Exit Structures*. DSD Working Papers on Research Security No.4, Social Science Research Council.

- Gentile, M. (2013). 'Meeting the "Organs": The Tacit Dilemma of Field Research in Authoritarian States', *Area*, No. 45, Vol. 4: 426-432.
- Huggins, M.K. and M.-L. Glebbeek (eds.) (2009). *Women Fielding Danger: Negotiating Ethnographic Identities in Field Research*, Lexington: Rowman and Littlefield.
- Ice, G., Dufour, D.L. and N. Stevens (2015). *Disasters in Field Research: Preparing for and Coping with Unexpected Events*, New York: Rowman & Littlefield.
- Kapiszewski, D., MacLean, L.M. and B. Read (2015). *Field Research in Political Science: Practices and Principles*, Cambridge: CUP.
- Knott, E. (2019) 'Beyond the Field: Ethics after Fieldwork in Politically Dynamic Contexts', *Perspectives on Politics*, No. 17, Vol. 1:140-153.
- Kovats-Bernat, J.C. (2002). 'Negotiating Dangerous Fields: Pragmatic Strategies for Fieldwork Amid Violence and Terror', *American Anthropologist*, No. 104, Vol. 1: 208-222.
- Lee-Treweek, G. and S. Linkogle (2000). *Danger in the Field. Ethics and Risk in Social Research*, London: Routledge.
- Lekha Sriram, C., King, J.C., J.A. Mertus, Martin-Ortega, O., and J. Herman (eds.) (2009). *Surviving Field Research. Working in Violent and Difficult Situations*. London: Routledge.
- Vanderbeck, R.M. (2005). 'Masculinities and Fieldwork: Widening the Discussion', *Gender, Place & Culture*, No. 12, Vol. 4: 387-402.
- Wackenhut, A.F. (2018). 'Ethical Considerations and Dilemmas before, during and after Fieldwork in Less Democratic Contexts: Some Reflections from Post-Uprising Egypt', *The American Sociologist*, No. 49, Vol. 2: 242-257.
- Wood, E.J. (2006). 'The Ethical Challenges of Field Research in Conflict Zones', *Qualitative Sociology*, No. 29: 373-386.